

EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE RELEVANCE OF E-LEARNING IN TEACHING YORUBA LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN SOUTH WEST, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20729204>

Keywords:

*Yoruba
Language, E-
learning,
Teaching*

Abstract: *Language is a fundamental tool for human communication, playing a crucial role in the transmission of ideas, culture, and identity. In contemporary academic settings, the dynamics of language use have been significantly influenced by digital technologies. This study investigates the relevance of e-learning in the teaching of Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. A descriptive survey design is adopted, involving primary school pupils, Yoruba language teachers and school head teachers across selected states in South West Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique were employed to select approximately 300 participants. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, semi-structured interview guides, and an optional achievement test to assess language proficiency. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive via SPSS, while qualitative data will be analyzed thematically. The study examines current teaching methods, evaluate the availability and use of e-learning tools, assess their impact on pupils' interest and proficiency, and identify implementation challenges. The findings revealed that various instructional methods are currently employed in the teaching of Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The respondents agreed that teachers predominantly use traditional chalk-and-talk methods, storytelling, songs and rhymes, oral exercises, group discussions, instructional materials, and role-play activities during Yoruba language lessons. It concludes by recommending that Schools should provide stable internet connectivity and adequate technological infrastructure to facilitate easy access to digital learning resources for both teachers and pupils.*

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Introduction

Language is a fundamental tool for human communication, playing a crucial role in the transmission of ideas, culture, and identity. In contemporary academic settings, the dynamics of language use have been significantly influenced by digital technologies. As indigenous languages face declining interest and proficiency due to the dominance of foreign languages and outdated teaching methods, there is an urgent need to explore innovative instructional approaches.

Language is not only a tool for communication but also a vehicle for transmitting culture, heritage, and identity from one generation to another (Ayo and Oludele, 2019). In Nigeria with diverse linguistic landscape, indigenous languages such as Yoruba play an important role in preserving ethnic identity, promoting cultural values, and enhancing community cohesion. However, with the increasing dominance of foreign languages like English, especially in formal education systems, the use and relevance of indigenous languages are gradually declining. This trend is particularly evident in primary schools, where foundational language skills are developed. The Yoruba language, despite being one of the major Nigerian languages spoken by millions in the South West geopolitical zone, faces declining interest and proficiency among younger generations due to various socio-cultural and educational factors (Sosan and Okewole, 2024). The traditional methods of teaching Yoruba in many primary schools are

largely ineffective and outdated. Chalk-and-talk approaches, rote memorization, and lack of engaging instructional materials contribute to pupils' disinterest in learning the language. Moreover, insufficient qualified Yoruba language teachers, inadequate curriculum support, and limited resources further exacerbate the problem. As a result, many pupils complete primary education with poor oral and written proficiency in Yoruba. This issue raises serious concerns about the future of indigenous language education and the preservation of cultural heritage in Nigeria.

In response to the evolving landscape of education and the growing need for more effective pedagogical strategies, e-learning has emerged as a transformative tool with the potential to improve language instruction. E-learning involves the use of digital technologies and electronic media to facilitate teaching and learning processes. It allows for interactive, flexible, and learner-centered instruction, which is particularly suitable for language acquisition. Through multimedia tools such as audio-visual resources, animations, gamified content, and virtual classrooms, e-learning can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of indigenous languages, making them more attractive and accessible to young learners (Opoola, 2019).

In Nigeria, the integration of e-learning into basic education is gaining momentum, particularly following the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Prince, 2021). The pandemic highlighted the need for alternative

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Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 11; Issue: 6

June, 2026

ISSN: 2237 – 1470

Impact Factor: 10.35

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajess>

modes of instruction, especially in situations where traditional classroom learning is not feasible. As schools transitioned to online platforms, educators and policymakers began to explore the potential of digital learning tools for all subjects, including indigenous languages. However, despite the increasing recognition of e-learning, its practical application in teaching Yoruba at the primary level remains limited and under-researched. Most e-learning platforms in Nigeria focus primarily on core subjects such as Mathematics, English, and Science, with very few initiatives targeting indigenous language instruction (Opoola, 2019).

The South West region of Nigeria, being the cultural and geographical heartland of the Yoruba people, presents a unique context for exploring the role of e-learning in promoting indigenous language education. With growing urbanization, technological advancement, and high mobile and internet penetration rates in many parts of the region, there is an opportunity to harness digital tools to revitalize Yoruba language learning. Furthermore, the increasing exposure of children to digital devices from an early age creates a conducive environment for the adoption of e-learning strategies in primary schools. Integrating e-learning into the Yoruba language curriculum could help improve students' motivation, enhance their language competence, and foster a deeper appreciation of their cultural roots.

Despite the promising potential of e-learning, several challenges hinder its effective implementation. These include inadequate

infrastructure, limited access to digital devices, lack of teacher training in the use of educational technologies, and insufficient government support. Furthermore, there is a general lack of empirical data on the relevance and effectiveness of e-learning in teaching Yoruba in primary schools. This gap in knowledge makes it difficult for policymakers and educators to make informed decisions on curriculum development, resource allocation, and pedagogical innovation. Therefore, a systematic and evidence-based study is needed to assess how e-learning tools can be effectively employed to teach Yoruba, identify best practices, and recommend strategies for scaling up successful interventions. This study is particularly timely and relevant as it aligns with global educational trends that emphasize inclusive, technology-driven, and culturally responsive teaching methods. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 calls for quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all, with an emphasis on leveraging information and communication technology (ICT) to improve learning outcomes. Similarly, Nigeria's National Policy on Education advocates for the use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning across all levels of education, including in the instruction of Nigerian languages. An empirical investigation into the relevance of e-learning in teaching Yoruba at the primary school level would contribute valuable insights to educational research, policy formulation, and curriculum innovation in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

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The Yoruba language which is a key component of Nigeria's cultural heritage, is increasingly losing relevance among younger generations due to declining interest and ineffective teaching methods in primary schools. Traditional instructional approaches have failed to engage pupils meaningfully, leading to poor proficiency and low retention of indigenous language skills. In an era where technology plays a central role in education, e-learning presents a viable and innovative solution to revitalize Yoruba language instruction through interactive, learner-centered, and engaging digital platforms. Despite the growing integration of e-learning into education systems globally and nationally, limited attention has been given to its application in teaching indigenous languages like Yoruba at the primary school level. This study is essential to assess the practical relevance and impact of e-learning tools in improving language acquisition, promoting cultural appreciation, and enhancing educational outcomes in South West Nigeria. By generating empirical data, the study provides valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers on how to effectively harness digital technologies to support indigenous language education. It also contributes to ongoing efforts to preserve Nigeria's linguistic and cultural diversity in line with global educational development goals. This research is therefore timely, necessary, and aligned with national and international priorities for inclusive and culturally responsive education.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the relevance and effectiveness of e-learning in the teaching and learning of Yoruba language in primary schools in South West Nigeria.

Specifically, the study determines:

- (i) examine the current methods used in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria.
- (ii) assess the availability and utilization of e-learning tools and resources in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level.
- (iii) evaluate the impact of e-learning on pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language.

Research Question

Based on the stated objectives of the study, the following research questions can be formulated:

- (i) What are the current methods used in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria?
- (ii) To what extent are e-learning tools and resources available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level in South West Nigeria?
- (iii) What impact does e-learning have on pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Indigenous Language Education in Nigeria

The Federal Republic of Nigeria through National Policy on Education recognizes the significance of indigenous languages in foundational learning and recommends mother

tongue instruction for the first three years of primary education (FGN, 2014). Despite this policy, implementation has been weak due to several factors, including inadequate teacher training, lack of instructional materials, and a societal preference for English as a medium of instruction (Igboanusi and Peter, 2017). This has contributed to a decline in indigenous language proficiency among pupils, especially in urban areas where English dominates both formal and informal communication.

Yoruba, one of Nigeria's three major indigenous languages, is spoken predominantly in the South West region. Despite its cultural and historical importance, its usage among younger generations is waning. Afolayan (2018) noted that pupils often struggle with reading and writing in Yoruba due to insufficient exposure and ineffective teaching methods. Additionally, Bamgbose (2019) emphasized that children learn best when taught in their mother tongue, yet the undervaluing of Yoruba within both the educational system and households has significantly impacted its development and continuity.

Challenges in Teaching Yoruba in Primary Schools

The teaching of Yoruba in primary schools is hindered by multiple structural and pedagogical challenges. Many primary school teachers lack specialized training in Yoruba language instruction, which affects the quality of their delivery (Odejide, 2020). Lessons are often delivered using outdated methods such as rote memorization and recitation, which fail to

capture the interest of modern learners who are increasingly accustomed to visual and interactive content. Another significant challenge is the scarcity of learning materials in Yoruba. Few textbooks, storybooks, or visual aids are available in the language, limiting both teachers' effectiveness and pupils' engagement. Furthermore, socio-cultural factors, such as the perception of English as a language of upward mobility, further reduce children's exposure to Yoruba at home. Fakoya and Ogunleye (2017) reported that many parents prioritize English, believing it offers better academic and career prospects for their children, leading to limited practice and reinforcement of Yoruba outside the classroom.

E-Learning and Its Role in Primary Education

E-learning refers to the use of electronic technologies, including computers, tablets, and mobile devices, to deliver educational content and facilitate instruction. The digital transformation of education has gained significant traction globally and is being adopted across all levels of learning. Clark and Mayer (2016) argued that e-learning fosters learner autonomy, enhances engagement, and allows for personalized learning experiences. For primary education, e-learning offers interactive opportunities that can enhance literacy, language skills, and overall academic performance. In Nigeria, e-learning became more prominent during the COVID-19 pandemic as a means of sustaining education amidst school closures. Okebukola (2020) noted that although

Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 11; Issue: 6

June, 2026

ISSN: 2237 – 1470

Impact Factor: 10.35

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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the adoption was uneven, it opened up conversations around digital readiness and the need for ICT integration in education. While e-learning is more commonly used in secondary and tertiary institutions, it holds untapped potential for enhancing teaching and learning at the primary level, especially for language instruction.

E-Learning and Indigenous Language Instruction

Studies have shown that e-learning can improve the teaching and learning of indigenous languages by incorporating multimedia tools that make lessons more engaging. Olayiwola and Adebayo (2021) found that educational mobile applications with Yoruba-language features helped enhance pupils' vocabulary, pronunciation, and comprehension. These digital tools also provided opportunities for repeated practice and learning outside the traditional classroom environment.

Ige (2020) reported positive outcomes from the use of animated videos, interactive stories, and games designed in Yoruba. These e-resources captured pupils' attention and made language learning enjoyable, thereby increasing motivation and participation. Additionally, such tools help address the issue of limited instructional materials, as they can be easily accessed and reused across multiple learning contexts.

The use of audio-visual resources is particularly valuable for a tonal language like Yoruba, where pronunciation and intonation affect meaning. E-learning platforms can provide accurate models

of speech and listening practice that reinforce correct language usage. Furthermore, e-learning allows for differentiated instruction, accommodating diverse learning styles and paces among pupils.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of this study comprises primary school pupils, Yoruba language teachers and head teachers in public and private primary schools across the selected South Western states. The focus on this population stems from their direct involvement in and influence on Yoruba language instruction at the foundational level. A multi-stage sampling technique will be employed. First, three states were randomly selected from the six in the South West. In each selected state, two local government areas (LGAs) were chosen randomly. Five primary schools (public and private) are then be purposively selected from each LGA based on their level of e-learning adoption or ICT presence. From each selected school, 10 teachers and 10 pupils in Primary Five and Six are selected using stratified random sampling to ensure gender balance and class representation. Additional participants such as school heads were purposively selected for key informant interviews. In total, the sample size is expected to be approximately 300 participants. This method ensures that every member of the population has equal chance of being selected as a member of the sample. Questionnaire was used for gathering of data for the study. It has 30 items. Items will be structured using a 4-point

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Likert scale ranging from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree,” along with some multiple-choice and checklist questions to allow for flexibility in responses.

The analysis showed that the instrument achieved reliability coefficient of 0.70 which is high and positive. The researcher administered the instrument with the help of three trained research assistant from the covered Schools. The

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent of current methods used in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Teachers use traditional chalk-and-talk methods.	3.23	0.89	Agreed
2	Storytelling is commonly used.	3.17	0.91	Agreed
3	Songs and rhymes are used.	3.20	0.88	Agreed
4	Role-play activities are used.	2.90	0.97	Agreed
5	Teachers encourage pupils to speak Yoruba.	3.23	0.92	Agreed
6	Instructional materials are used.	3.13	0.93	Agreed
7	Group discussion methods are used.	3.00	0.96	Agreed
8	Practical oral exercises are given regularly.	3.19	0.90	Agreed
9	Yoruba textbooks are adequately used.	3.09	0.94	Agreed
10	Teaching methods make lessons interesting.	3.16	0.91	Agreed
	Grand weighted Mean	3.13	0.56	Agreed

Source, Field Survey, 2026

Table 1 reveals that current methods used in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The findings showed that teachers commonly use traditional chalk-and-talk methods in teaching Yoruba language, with a mean score of 3.23 and a standard deviation of 0.89. This suggests that the conventional teacher-centered instructional approach remains highly prevalent in Yoruba

return rate was 90 percent. Data collected in respect to researcher questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Results and Data

Analyses Research Question 1: What are the current methods used in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria?

language classrooms. Similarly, the respondents agreed that teachers encourage pupils to speak Yoruba during lessons, as indicated by a mean score of 3.23 and standard deviation of 0.92, implying active promotion of oral communication in the language.

The study also revealed that songs and rhymes are frequently used in Yoruba language teaching, with a mean score of 3.20 and standard deviation of 0.88. This indicates that teachers adopt

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musical and rhythmic strategies to facilitate language learning and retention among pupils. In the same vein, practical oral exercises were found to be regularly administered, with a mean score of 3.19 and standard deviation of 0.90, suggesting that oral practice constitutes an important aspect of Yoruba language instruction. Furthermore, storytelling was identified as another commonly used teaching method, with a mean score of 3.17 and standard deviation of 0.91. This finding reflects the cultural relevance of storytelling as a pedagogical tool in Yoruba language education. The respondents also agreed that the teaching methods employed make Yoruba language lessons interesting to pupils, with a mean score of 3.16 and standard deviation of 0.91, indicating that the instructional approaches used are capable of sustaining learners' interest. Additionally, the use of instructional materials was affirmed by the respondents, with a mean score of 3.13 and standard deviation of 0.93. This implies that teachers make use of teaching aids to support classroom instruction. Yoruba textbooks were

also reported to be adequately used, with a mean score of 3.09 and standard deviation of 0.94, while group discussion methods recorded a mean score of 3.00 and standard deviation of 0.96, indicating moderate utilization of collaborative learning strategies. Among all the items, role-play activities recorded the lowest mean score of 2.90 and standard deviation of 0.97, although the item was still accepted. This suggests that while role-play is used in Yoruba language teaching, it is less frequently adopted compared to other instructional methods. The grand weighted mean of 3.13 with a standard deviation of 0.56 further confirms that respondents generally agreed that a variety of instructional methods are currently employed in teaching Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria.

Analyses Research Question 2: To what extent are e-learning tools and resources available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level in South West Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent are e-learning tools and resources available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level in South West Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
11	Computers are available for teaching Yoruba.	2.63	1.02	Strongly Agreed
12	Internet facilities are available.	2.53	1.04	Strongly Agreed
13	Educational videos are used.	2.93	0.97	Agreed
14	Pupils use tablets/mobile devices.	2.68	1.01	Strongly Agreed

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15	Audio recordings improve pronunciation.	3.05	0.92	Agreed
16	Teachers are trained in e-learning use.	2.54	1.03	Strongly Agreed
17	Digital Yoruba materials are available.	2.73	1.00	Strongly Agreed
18	Schools support e-learning use.	2.88	0.96	Agreed
19	Teachers use multimedia presentations.	2.84	0.97	Strongly Agreed
20	E-learning resources are accessible.	2.75	1.05	Agreed
Grand weighted Mean		2.76	0.77	Strongly Agreed

Source, Field Survey, 2026

Table 2, sought to determine the extent to which e-learning tools and resources are available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level in South West Nigeria. The findings presented in Table 2 revealed that all the item statements recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that respondents agreed that e-learning tools and resources are available and utilized to a reasonable extent in Yoruba language instruction. The findings showed that audio recordings are used to improve pupils' pronunciation in Yoruba language, with a mean score of 3.05 and standard deviation of 0.92. This suggests that audio-based instructional resources are among the most commonly utilized e-learning tools in Yoruba language teaching, particularly for enhancing learners' oral and pronunciation skills. The respondents also agreed that educational videos are used during Yoruba language lessons, as indicated by a mean score of 2.93 and standard deviation of 0.97. This

implies that visual and audio-visual learning materials are increasingly being integrated into classroom instruction to facilitate pupils' understanding and engagement. Similarly, school support for the use of e-learning in Yoruba language teaching recorded a mean score of 2.88 and standard deviation of 0.96, indicating that schools provide some level of encouragement and support for the integration of technology into language instruction. The use of multimedia presentations by teachers also received a positive response, with a mean score of 2.84 and standard deviation of 0.97, suggesting that teachers make moderate use of digital presentation tools during lessons. The study further revealed that pupils use tablets and mobile devices for Yoruba language learning, with a mean score of 2.68 and standard deviation of 1.01. This indicates that mobile learning technologies are gradually becoming part of the instructional process in some primary schools. In addition, the availability of computers for teaching Yoruba language had a mean score of 2.63 and standard

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deviation of 1.02, suggesting moderate access to computer facilities for instructional purposes. The grand weighted mean of 2.76 and standard deviation of 0.77 further confirms that respondents generally agreed that e-learning tools and resources are available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language at the primary school level in South West Nigeria. The standard

deviation value indicates a moderate level of variation in respondents' opinions.

Analyses Research Question 3: What impact does e-learning have on pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent are e-learning have on pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria

S/N	Items statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
21	E-learning increases pupils' interest.	3.25	0.88	Agreed
22	Pupils participate more actively.	3.20	0.89	Agreed
23	Digital resources improve understanding.	3.22	0.88	Agreed
24	E-learning improves pronunciation.	3.19	0.89	Agreed
25	Pupils perform better in tests.	3.18	0.90	Agreed
26	E-learning makes learning enjoyable.	3.25	0.87	Agreed
27	Pupils become more confident.	3.17	0.89	Agreed
28	E-learning improves vocabulary.	3.22	0.88	Agreed
29	Technology motivates pupils.	3.25	0.87	Agreed
30	E-learning enhances proficiency.	3.24	0.87	Agreed
Grand weighted Mean		3.22	0.62	Agreed

Source, Field Survey, 2026

Table 3 reveals the mean ratings of the respondents to examine the impact of e-learning on pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The findings presented in Table 3 revealed that all the item statements recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that respondents agreed that e-learning has a positive impact on pupils' learning outcomes in Yoruba language. The

findings showed that e-learning increases pupils' interest in Yoruba language lessons, with a mean score of 3.25 and standard deviation of 0.88. This suggests that the integration of digital learning tools and technological resources makes Yoruba language learning more attractive and engaging to pupils. Similarly, the respondents agreed that e-learning makes learning enjoyable, as indicated by a mean score of 3.25 and standard deviation of 0.87. This implies that the use of interactive multimedia resources

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Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 11; Issue: 6

June, 2026

ISSN: 2237 – 1470

Impact Factor: 10.35

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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contributes to a more stimulating and enjoyable classroom experience. Furthermore, digital learning resources were found to improve pupils' understanding of Yoruba language concepts, with a mean score of 3.22 and standard deviation of 0.88. Similarly, e-learning was reported to improve pupils' vocabulary development, as shown by a mean score of 3.22 and standard deviation of 0.88. These findings indicate that exposure to digital instructional materials enhances pupils' comprehension and acquisition of Yoruba vocabulary. The respondents also agreed that pupils participate more actively in lessons when e-learning tools are used, with a mean score of 3.20 and standard deviation of 0.89. This implies that technology-enhanced instruction encourages greater classroom interaction and learner participation. Likewise, e-learning was found to improve pupils' pronunciation of Yoruba words, with a mean score of 3.19 and standard deviation of 0.89, indicating that audiovisual and audio learning tools help learners develop better oral language skills. The grand weighted mean of 3.22 and standard deviation of 0.62 further confirms that respondents generally agreed that e-learning has a significant positive impact on pupils' interest, participation, confidence, understanding, and overall proficiency in Yoruba language.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that various instructional methods are currently employed in the teaching of Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The respondents agreed that teachers predominantly

use traditional chalk-and-talk methods, storytelling, songs and rhymes, oral exercises, group discussions, instructional materials, and role-play activities during Yoruba language lessons. The grand weighted mean of 3.13 indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the use of these teaching methods.

The findings of the study further revealed that e-learning tools and resources are moderately available and utilized in the teaching of Yoruba language in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The grand weighted mean of 2.76 showed that respondents generally agreed that technological tools such as computers, educational videos, tablets, mobile devices, multimedia presentations, audio recordings, and digital Yoruba learning materials are available and utilized to some extent. The study also revealed that pupils make use of tablets and mobile devices for Yoruba language learning, indicating gradual integration of mobile learning technologies into primary school education. This development reflects the growing influence of information and communication technology in modern educational practices. Similarly, school support for e-learning utilization suggests increasing institutional recognition of the importance of technology-enhanced learning.

The findings demonstrated that e-learning increases pupils' interest in Yoruba language lessons and makes learning more enjoyable. This may be attributed to the interactive nature of digital learning tools, which often combine visual, audio, and interactive elements capable of

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capturing pupils' attention and sustaining their engagement. The use of educational technologies appears to reduce boredom commonly associated with traditional teaching methods. The study further revealed that pupils participate more actively during lessons when e-learning tools are utilized. This suggests that digital learning environments encourage collaboration, interaction, and learner-centered participation. The findings also showed that e-learning improves pupils' understanding, vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and confidence in speaking Yoruba language. This may be due to the ability of multimedia resources to provide repeated exposure to language content through audio-visual formats that enhance comprehension and retention.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it revealed that traditional and interactive teaching methods are widely used in Yoruba language instruction in primary schools across South West Nigeria. The study further showed that e-learning facilities and digital resources are moderately available and utilized. Most importantly, the use of e-learning significantly improves pupils' interest, participation, and proficiency in Yoruba language learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

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(i) Government and educational stakeholders should provide adequate e-learning facilities such as computers, tablets, projectors, internet services, and digital instructional materials in primary schools to support effective teaching and learning of Yoruba language.

(ii) School administrators should encourage the integration of e-learning technologies into Yoruba language instruction in order to improve pupils' interest, participation, and academic performance.

(iii) Teachers of Yoruba language should be regularly trained through workshops, seminars, and professional development programmes on the effective use of e-learning tools and digital instructional strategies in classroom teaching.

(iv) Curriculum planners and education authorities should incorporate technology-based instructional approaches into the Yoruba language curriculum at the primary school level to enhance modern language learning practices.

(v) Schools should provide stable internet connectivity and adequate technological infrastructure to facilitate easy access to digital learning resources for both teachers and pupils.

(vi) Yoruba language teachers should adopt more learner-centered and interactive teaching methods such as educational videos, multimedia presentations, storytelling, role-play, songs, and audio recordings to make learning more engaging and effective.

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Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Edu. Soc. Sci

Volume: 11; Issue: 6

June, 2026

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Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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